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The relationship between Job satisfaction and Emotional qution and organization commitment Physical education office staff of Tehran universities

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was studying the relationship between Emotional qution, Job satisfaction and organization commitment physical education office staff of Tehran universities. The statistical population of the study was included 130 people (114 experts of government universities and 16 experts of non-government universities) samples.

The instrument of the study was questionnaires made by shiring and et all (emotional qution), porters and et all (job satisfaction), Meyer JP, Allen JN (Organization Commitment). In this research the use of descriptive Method, also average, standard deviation and inference like pierson correlation and multiple regressions. There was significant correlation respectively between Emotional qution and Job satisfaction ($r=0/3$, $P\leq 01/0$), Emotional qution and organization commitment ($r=0/35$, $P\leq 0/01$), Job satisfaction and organization commitment ($r=0/69$, $P\leq 0/01$). Also, there were multiple the relationships between Emotional qution and Job satisfaction, Emotional qution and organization commitment. ($F =9/23$, $R2=0/19$, $P\leq 0/001$) and ($F=8/05$, $R2=0/17$, $P\leq 0/001$).

According to results of the study it seems authority submission to worthy staff, improving team working, workshop to introducing emotional qution and suitable using in workplace, can effectiveness in improving organization commitment in physical education office of universities.

Keywords: Emotional qution, Job satisfaction, organization commitment

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